

Digital Well-Being in Castilla y León, a New Opportunity for the Tourism Sector

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ABSTRACT

In recent years we are experiencing great changes worldwide that lead to rethinking and looking at things from other points of view. The search for digital well-being brings us closer to the adoption of healthy lifestyle habits using the technology that surrounds us. Because of this the Community of Castilla y León in Spain, rich in history, traditions and culture, finds technology useful to endorse its entire tourist tradition, as an example of the relationship between aspects of healthy living and the use of digital technology. These factors allow a sustainable tourism that is necessary at this time when resources are beginning to feel limited; something that have been seen very necessary throughout the COVID-19 pandemic. In this study, we discussed the changes provoke by COVID-19 pandemic using a geographical case study focused on Castilla y León. We discussed the results relative to digital well-being in tourism and its influence in local enterprises.

KEYWORDS

Digital Well-Being, Tourism, Castilla León, Spain, Enterprise

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1. Introduction

Due to its ancient historical configuration, Europe has developed a series of regions that currently form part of different states. Throughout history, these regions have been forming states, sometimes changing countries, and establishing borders that have changed for political or military reasons (Barbosa et al., 2020). The map that we have today is the fruit of years of changes, conflicts, agreements and treaties that have delimited Europe and that, as we have been able to observe in recent events, create a fragile balance of power.

Spain is one of the oldest nations in Europe, and due to its peninsular orography and its separation from the continent by a large mountain range, its borders have remained practically unchanged since its formation. Despite being made up of several ancient kingdoms, Spain never had a strong regional feeling in the past. At the same time, she developed a strong sense of belonging to the Province, a political entity inferior to that of the region. This feeling is described in numerous literary works such as *Los Pazos de Ulloa*, and is pejoratively described with the term provincial or provincialism.

The Spanish Constitution of 1978 enshrines parliamentary democracy with a modern and current legal text, advanced for its time and even today, as it served as an example to the Baltic countries after the disappearance of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics and to the countries of the North after the Arab springs. This Constitution proposes transcending the old provincialism by establishing the regionalism that in Spain is called autonomism by the name of the Entity that is the Autonomous Community.

The Autonomous Community of Castilla y León is built on two historical kingdoms and nine provinces. In the area there was no regional feeling and there was a very strong and marked provincialism. The Spanish Constitution imposes a mandate to develop the regions or Autonomous Communities in all their dimensions. This work is carried out from different sectors and one of them is the media, especially the local or regional ones. These media contribute to the constitutional mandate, as we can amply affirm, structuring the two historical kingdoms now as a single entity, and transcending what belongs to a region to become part of a community, in a broader political and legal entity.

With this advance, a new regional directive body is created, an elite body, superior to the provincial one, which works to favor new specific sectors that were previously unthinkable or incompatible with provincialism. One of them is tourism. Castilla y León is the region of Spain with the most cathedrals, castles and monuments of Romanesque art in general. It is still a very characteristic area of Spain since at the time of its union they decided not to put a capital within that Community, as is the case with the Basque Country. This shows that there was no great feeling of community, but there was a clear belonging to the land and the common space they inhabit.

The inhabitants of the Community of Castilla y León feel with pride how the characteristics of the land they inhabit present them, without a doubt, as one of the tourist strongholds of Spain. No one can pass through this land without visiting the Babia area with its characteristic mountains, the Tuerces with its gigantic stone turtles, the Arribes del Duero, the Burgos waterfalls, the Fuentona with its Lobo River canyon, the wine route of Cigales, the aqueduct of Segovia, the walls of Ávila or Puebla de Sanabria, among many other magical spaces where time freezes and nature absorbs you. There are few communities that have such a great variety of history and nature and allow so many different activities to be carried out within a short space of time. This means that Castilla y León, which was already a model in traditional tourism development, can prepare itself in a very complete way for another type of tourism.

All these spaces present Castilla y León as the leader by extension in inland tourism, also known as rural tourism and, one must add that more than a third of the surface of the region does not have access to the Internet, which is Flame Digital Shadow. This is due to the complicated orography of the territory which has large mountains and mountain ranges. These natural spaces are authentic jewels which combine diverse natural ecosystems to show nature in its maximum expression and they attract a type of tourism which is so in demand today. But these same natural areas sometimes make it difficult to extend digitization because their very orography makes it difficult and today many of these spaces have yet to receive the arrival of 5G, which is so crucial to the absorption of everything the fourth industrial Revolution offers. This particularity, which is seen as a great problem of economic development, can be used as an opportunity for the development of "Digital Well-Being", and the local and regional media, as in the

development of autonomy, will have an active role (Beetham, 2016; Kumar et al., 2020).

That is why, using an inductive-deductive methodology, we will address the potentialities of this digital well-being in the limited environment of the Community of Castilla y León and learn how it can help promote a differential tourism that emphasizes and personalizes the benefits of this territory that has so much in history and natural resources, characterizing it as one of the most significant places in the kingdom of Spain.

The objective of this research is to address digital wellness tourism as a new form of disconnection, relating it to the territory of Castilla y León, which offers very significant opportunities for this new recreation that the digital media are already picking up. This new field, despite the fact that it has been analyzed by many other authors, has not been developed in relation to the peculiarities of the Castilian-Leones territory that offers, due to its own singularities, great opportunities for this new model which have not been highlighted by others. The most significant finding that we have achieved after completing this article is to understand how the region of Castilla y León fulfills all the conditions expected to achieve this new digital wellness tourism and how this new leisure model puts it ahead of other Areas of the Iberian Peninsula.

2. Literature Review

The potential of rural space in Castilla y León has been analyzed for several years by different authors who have reflected on the possibilities of these spaces in different articles (Saiz Martín, 2013). (Alario Trigueros et al., 2018). This new tourism goes hand in hand with an increase in motivation and the need to remove oneself from a markedly digital world. All the authors who have studied the role of motivation in digital wellness coincide in affirming that it is a determining factor within the new digital environments (Saura et al., 2021; Ostic et al., 2021).

Generally, there are two types of motivation which arise in the process of a change of mind. First, extrinsic motivation which refers to that which is used as an instrument to achieve an end (Botella & Ramos, 2019). The person motivated by this type of motivation does not do it personally, but acts influenced by external factors (Botella & Ramos, 2019). In turn, Usán and Salavera (2018) classify this motivation into types according to the degree of self-determination that occurs. On the other hand, intrinsic motivation, the one that has a personal basis, which derives from the individual (Usán & Salavera, 2018; Hernández & Cordero, 2021). In this sense, motivation comes from a free personal choice, without being influenced by external factors (Botella & Ramos, 2019). This type of motivation causes us to act following a personal decision to achieve a goal that we have set for ourselves and that satisfies us individually. As Usán and Salavera (2018) state, it is a motivation that does not imply any external reinforcement and is directed either towards stimulating experiences that entail fun, or towards the development of knowledge for the pleasure of learning, or towards the attainment of an achievement that helps us outdo ourselves. In this sense, the new digital well-being that is related to digital tourism seeks to ensure that people's motivation leads them to new experiences of leisure together with disconnection and that is why it is important to analyze the motivation for this type of new state of wellness (Belo et al., 2014; Agapito et al., 2014).

The recent pandemic has made clear the need to look for new spaces where we can find ourselves in a different way, presenting the new tourism related to digital well-being as a primary need (Suchada & Patsachon, 2022). Among younger people who live in a more connected world, this digital wellness and disconnection tourism has become fundamental and that, as many authors tell us, is sought with more intensity every day (Anannukul & Yoopetch, 2022). The research question is as follows. After a moment of pandemic in which we have experienced a great moment of digital connection under the protection of the fourth industrial revolution, a new phenomenon of tourism is taking place. This new model seeks to unite digital disconnection with wellness tourism. Can the territory of Castilla y León be a model of this new digital wellness tourism thanks to its clear peculiarities?

In addition, many of the authors present this new method of tourism related to digital as a new phenomenon of social integration that must be closely tracked due to its importance. The authors highlight how this model is becoming very widespread in rural areas, seeking and adding other geographical attractions to this new tourism model (Hassan et al., 2022).

The work provided in this article shows us the use of digital well-being related to the new type of tourism in conjunction with the unique characteristics offered by the Community of Castilla y León that make it, as we analyzed, an example within Spain and with a view to other model areas of a new type of tourism that must still be analyzed in order to establish it safely.

Everything analyzed leads us to demonstrate how the new generations of digital natives are looking for a new model of tourism marked by a new way of seeing things. Castilla y León is becoming the backbone of this new type of tourism in Spain. Its regional characteristics and its openness towards this new transformation towards this new public show us how the appropriate changes can be made for a new leisure model that is based on the foundations of the need for a digital disconnection.

3. Methodology

In this article we have carried out an applied investigation. In the words of Cívicos and Hernández, (2007) applied research is characterized by the way of studying social reality, placing the resolution of social problems ahead of scientific interest, in order to apply its discoveries to the improvement of different strategies and certain social actions (Cívicos & Hernández, 2007). Regarding the nature of the study, an analytical investigation will be carried out that requires the analysis of different forms of analysis of forms of digital wellness tourism (Quecedo & Castaño, 2002). The research design is going to be of an experimental type, since the researcher guides and controls one or more independent variables and analyzes the dependent variable(s) to assess concurrent variations (Agudelo et al., 2008; Saura et al., 2021a).

4. Analysis of Results

The Covid 19 pandemic forced the immediate digitization of society, in a process that accelerated access to technology. Rapid transformations sometimes do not accompany biological transformations, sometimes generating episodes of great stress. That is why experts have been talking about technological addictions for a long time and after the pandemic the concept of Digital Well-Being emerges. This is a concept that highlights the need to analyze the excessive use that is made of all these new technologies. Companies have already begun to become aware of these issues and recently Mark Zuckerberg (founder of Facebook and owner of Instagram) conducted a study on addictions to “likes” within social networks. This study continues to be a sample of the social concern that exists in the face of that digital image that every person possesses. In addition, the Instagram study continues to be a clear example of society's concern for the new models of social relationships that generation Z has and that are anticipated in the Alpha Generation (the authentic digital natives who were born and are going to develop in a digital society). All this has been thoroughly analyzed and we live in a time when the X called digital immigrants, using the concept that Prensky defined as those who moved with technology but without control of it, coexist with the Y, Z and Alpha, who are true digital natives (Saura et al., 2021b).

These new generations are people whose leisure, work and day-to-day life are supported by this digitization but who increasingly need a point of disconnection given that analyzes of the excessive use of technology demonstrate the need to achieve spaces of freedom without using the new media (Olson & Heejung, 2021). The new metaverse that is beginning to take shape shows us how life is going to develop in a digital world in which companies like McDonald's they are asking for franchises of their new restaurants since they anticipate that the new technologies linked to this virtual world will favor new leisure models linked to a large digital presence of people who will dedicate much of their time to this digital world. Given all this, the Digital concept of Well-Being is not only imposed as a new model of relationship with technology but also as a need embodied by our new models of life and a search for healthier and more sustainable living spaces that share with what society demands at this time (Saura et al., 2022).

Recalling the implementation of the vacation period or the rest days imposed after the Industrial Revolution, Digital Well-Being must now begin to be considered as a fundamental part of the development of people. Historically speaking, the models have already presented us with the need to preserve the health of human beings in spite of the addictions that modern society presents, but the adoption of these new attitudes or methodologies must start from the understanding of the need to seek union between the

modern, the sustainable and the healthy that puts the human being at the center of all this analysis with the needs that are anticipated from this world of the fourth industrial revolution (Youngjoon et al., 2022). This digital well-being is forged within the search for healthier lifestyle habits in an increasingly digital world where we can forget the house keys but we cannot forget the element of relationship with that digital world which is normally a Smartphone with which we connect to and relate to every day more and more.

All of this makes us look at Castilla y Le3n from the new approach that this type of tourism offers and makes us understand how the spaces for digital disconnection offered by the multitude of places for tourism in this community serve to make it possible to establish a tourism that is different from the one that we already have samples of and that serves to show a new model of holiday health so in demand in this digital world. The tourist spaces of Castilla y Le3n have been for many years and are now fundamental elements of holiday difference and now, with the changes carried out, they are presented as the benchmark for a new model of leisure with very distinct characteristics (Ja3nez Garc3a, 2015; Saura et al., 2022a).

5. Discussion

The autonomous community of Castilla y Le3n has presented great peculiarities that present it as a unique example within the kingdom of Spain. All the momentum of its public administration has conceived a government standard forged to adapt, with flexibility, to the eventualities that occur at every turn, using the communication standard which it created, to modulate an address aimed at society and public opinion capable of legitimizing public policies and forging a significant feeling of excitement in the Castilian and Leonese regional community. The Community of Castilla y Le3n has significant peculiarities, and it has achieved that, over the years, those peculiarities that initially seemed like obstacles that favored a future separation, have become values that anchor their union and favor the contributions that each one of its individuals can perform for the common good. The community has also known how to merge with the new digital communication elements to promote a new communication model, as we can see in examples such as Bierzo Digital. These new elements of digital communication seek global communication in conjunction with the social networks that are so present today and, in recent times, have benefited the adoption of Digital Wellbeing measures, promoting the image of a Community that not only complies with the highest quality standards in tourism but also helps a different type of tourism seizing on these new practices that society is demanding. This Community becomes an example and a reference and opens the panorama to carry out significant actions within any field. Its history and its development have made it unique and have made it possible for other communities to observe its model of digital transformation, since it is the basis of development in the 21st century. This digital transformation, as we have said, also covers digital communication, which becomes the exponential center of any development that you want to present in the digital landscape to achieve maximum optimization.

Tourism communication in the digital age, together with new elements, is already something that has spread worldwide. In all countries, endorsed by large search engines, possibilities of a new type of tourism based on digital well-being are being offered digitally. Examples of all this can be found in different types of tourism such as that offered in New York, The Maldives, South Africa, Peru, Chile or Australia among many others. What we must understand is that although the need for this digital well-being is something ordained and established which does not present any type of doubt when it comes to defining it, this is not the case with the characteristics that this digital well-being tourism must offer since there are many examples that we can find that seem to put on the seal of digital well-being as a way of differentiation, rather than a well-defined quality standard that allows selecting the best spaces.

It is for all these reasons that we must clearly define this digital wellness tourism and within the most present characteristics worldwide we would highlight two main characteristics: A space where we can find a positive effect on our health and a space where we can control our relationship with technology. There would be many other characteristics but those two would encompass what we are looking for with this digital wellness tourism that we can find clearly present in the Community of Castilla y Le3n since, through the media, a differential type of tourism is presented that allows the clear union between nature and urban planning, making it possible to achieve spaces in which there is the possibility of a digital dis-

connection incited by the natural wonders in which one finds oneself, which demonstrates the need not to be hyper-connected all the time (García, 1999).

Digital well-being is linked to appropriate habits for the use of technology but not to a forced digital disconnection. Many link digital disconnection with digital well-being without understanding that well-being goes hand in hand with a willingness to be connected and not with a lack of means or resources to achieve that connection. We must understand that digital well-being in relation to tourism is linked to people being able to choose healthier lifestyle habits within the time they dedicate to this differential tourism and that it is giving so many good experiences worldwide. For both technology providers and users, digital well-being is becoming a key element that must be developed and this sector presents itself as a great opportunity for all countries and tour operators to carry out different good leisure practices. After the COVID-19 pandemic, a moment of breakout is demanded that distances us from the excessive use we have made of technology and that favors, as we have said, new approaches and new ways of relating to technology.

6. Digital Well-Being and Tourism, a Sector in Possible Development

As we have already highlighted, digital well-being is fundamental in the world we live in. If we analyze historically this path walked by the workers we can go back to the first industrial revolution where there was no search for well-being of the people who worked in the factories since that revolution was not focused on them, but on maximizing production to achieve Better benefits.

All the revolutions that have occurred throughout the history of humanity have been backed by the need for rupture. This rupture of the old with the new posed, without a doubt, a moment of uncertainty and opportunity. It was, for many, a moment of leaning over a real precipice since it forced them to adapt and reinvent themselves in the hope of being able to keep up with everything that was happening. This was so in the first industrial revolution when machines began to enter factories, which for many was a great threat since it separated them from the reality they had known until then. That first revolution backed by coal brought with it an authentic socio-economic change without comparison that largely laid the foundations for the schools that we know today, since the aim was to train students who would respond to the needs of this new society that emerged in the light of these momentous changes (Hobsbawm, 2009).

The second industrial revolution came hand in hand with the extensive use of electricity and knew how to absorb those machines that emerged in the first revolution to complete the automation processes of factories, generating large and extensive assembly lines that improved production and massified the creation of products. This revolution consolidated the first and, to a large extent, shaped capitalism and the international order that would mark the following years and is still present today (Haradhan, 2019).

The third industrial revolution was the implementation of ICT as a need to assume the existing digitization. It was a revolution that absorbed the automation of the second industrial revolution and gave it a backbone in the shadow of the growing use of the internet as part of the process. This revolution was quite fast, lasting from 1969, when Arpanet emerged as a communication element between universities after its military past, to the arrival of the World Wide Web in 1991, since not many years passed and that is why this revolution emerged with conditions that separated those who had not been born with that technology from those who had. The term adopted by Prensky in 2001 to differentiate digital immigrants (born before 1980) from digital natives (born after 1980) helps us to understand the fragmentation that this revolution entailed and all the changes that were integrated with those previously existing machines (Prensky, 2017). From that moment on, different initiatives were sought to spread digital literacy throughout the world, given that the integration of new technologies in all sectors of the population have demanded the need for digital skills in workers who, in some aspects, have resisted them (Taalbi, 2019).

And finally, we come to the fourth industrial revolution that for many authors is the one we are experiencing at the present time. It is a revolution that is supported by the spread of 5G, the internet of things, the implementation of artificial intelligence in everyday world, digital coordination, the spread of robotics in all work sectors and the use of cyber-physical systems (Gómez Salgado, 2021). For many, this revolution is going to be the most fragmenting of all the revolutions that we have gone through, since it supposes assuming a cyberconnected planet and a use of digital consciousness at a global level that none of the

previous revolutions achieved despite the existence of multiple threats (Saura, Palos-Sánchez & Navalpótro, 2018).

Faced with this great change, there are a large number of opposing positions regarding this revolution, since where some see opportunities, others see threats, which up to now has slowed down the implementation of all the necessary changes that are needed for the complete implementation of a revolution such as this one. It is paradoxical that many authors such as Aldous Huxley anticipated, many years in advance, the reality that this revolution presents us with its lights and shadows, which would be endorsed by that transhumanist term as a reference to overcoming the physical or intellectual limits of humans through the use of technology. That transhumanism for many is the hope for change in a cyberconnected world since it seeks to go beyond the physical barriers of humanity in order to expand the frontiers of knowledge, which is expected to be achieved in this nascent revolution. It is at this point in the fourth industrial revolution that we find the concept of digital well-being present. Machines are going to improve people's lives, but if we do not take advantage of this improvement in life to find spaces of communion between the person and the environment, leaving aside all digital connection, we will not be able to take advantage of this revolution adequately.

We cannot fail to emphasize everything that has happened during the pandemic when talking about digital well-being. For history, 2020 will be a year marked on the calendar by a pandemic, but if we see it in perspective, the history of humanity is full of pandemics that devastated humanity. One of the greatest examples can be found with the polio epidemic that devastated the United States in 1955. Then, as now, the closure of schools and the confinement of many areas of population were ordered. At that time, so that the students would not miss class, it was decided that all clases would all be given through the radio, which shows us once again how education prevails despite all the adversities that occur (Altenbaugh, 2006).

If we go back further, we can understand that humanity has always lived under the shadow of small viruses ending human existence. The bubonic plague or the Spanish flu are authentic examples of this, and their study helps us to understand how the human being prevails against everything and seeks to improve in every way. In the same way, what happened due to the COVID 19 pandemic has served to transform society, but we must not look at it only in a reformist spirit, we also have to delve into the intrinsic changes derived from everything that has happened in order to analyze the present possibilities and the past difficulties.

The arrival of the fourth industrial revolution, despite the fact that some authors consider that we have not yet fully entered into it, is perceived as something unstoppable. New technologies have been, and are, a disruptive element that change people and their mentalities. But this disruptive element must also be contained, and people must find moments of recreation that bring them closer to other types of experiences within the 21st century since hyperconnection, as has been shown during the pandemic, causes a digital addiction in certain sectors that can endanger the well-being and health of people, so we must be able to find a different leisure model.

Here enters the possibility of looking for another type of tourism that helps people to adequately unite the possibilities of that fourth industrial revolution and the need for a break that is clearly significant. In this, digital well-being as a space for new tourism arises with many possibilities. For the tourism sectors, proposing this new model of remote tourism or controlling the digital, implies the appearance of new spaces that help the person not only obtain what they like but also to be able to establish a type of health that their active rhythm of daily life demands. The leisure of the different generations (X, Y, Z and alpha) as we have mentioned before, is very different, but everyone is looking, as we have seen during the pandemic, for disconnection spaces that improve their digital well-being.

The characteristics of this digital well-being are clear and despite the fact that the large technological platforms are already offering disconnection spaces, the tourism industry still needs to fully adapt to this new sector that offers so many possibilities. These characteristics lead us to understand that everything focuses on two simple characteristics: Disconnection spaces with the possibility of connection and places that favor a type of emotional tourism that helps to achieve disconnection. These two characteristics can be completed with many other approaches that have been taking place in recent times around this new type of tourism, but the fundamental thing is that it seeks to link the digital world with the need to be able

to put a space for peace in the midst of all this daily maelstrom (Sigala, 2019). The possibilities of this new type of tourism are endless and open up new tourism possibilities after the time of confinement that we have experienced caused by COVID-19.

In all of this, as we have been able to analyze, the possibilities of this digital well-being that we can find in Castilla y León are incredible. Communication elements such as Bierzo Digital, among others, have known how to extend and bring to the consumer the unique characteristics that this Community offers due to its own historical roots, its characteristic makeup, its physical space, its innumerable artistic attractions, its gastronomy and a long etcetera that they already revealed the Community of Castilla y León as one of the places in Spain that, without being a coastal destination, attracted a greater number of tourists. These magnificent possibilities and the recent attempts to show this differential tourism using the need for digital well-being as a distinctive element make the possibilities of this community to become a leader in this tourism infinite. Practices have already been carried out that have shown that this type of tourism works perfectly and favors the health and well-being of the people who visit this community (Rico, 2005).

7. Conclusion

As we have already been able to analyze throughout this article, the Spanish Constitution develops the regional sentiment that did not exist before in Castilla y León. That feeling endows this space with uniqueness and presents it as a place of great possibilities in many ways where communication is very important to be able to coordinate the different actions in favor of this community.

Castilla y León has a great historical and cultural heritage and a complicated orography with mountains, which keeps more than a third of its territory in digital and Internet shadow. That makes it the perfect space for the development of another type of tourism, one that is highly demanded in this hyperconnected world that combines rest-health-disconnection. This tourism is presented as an ideal opportunity for development within Castilla y León where we can find great possibilities of digital disconnection together with a strengthening of mental health spaces that are demanded by society.

The great changes in humanity have always been a fragmentation between the previous and the following. There is no doubt that the COVID-19 pandemic has been a moment of important change and social relations are being reviewed in all sectors of the population to find a way to prepare for future pandemics. It is in this field where the fourth industrial revolution is coming and it is something which is very necessary since it meets the urgent need for a transhumanization that is being demanded socially, not only as a search for human improvement but as a response to a society that seeks the need of avoiding physical contacts as a form of prophylaxis, The fourth revolution is beginning and we can glimpse, with everything analyzed, the great possibilities that it offers us.

In the field of education, everything related to 5G, the internet of things or Artificial Intelligence will finally allow for the individualization of learning and consolidate the learning of skills and abilities that are so much in demand today. It is at this point where this pandemic has forced us to delve deeper into the changes favored by this revolution and all educational levels have perceived the benefits of a system where digitization acquires a greater role. But this digitization present in the fourth industrial revolution is also perceived as an element of addiction among many of the different generations that live together in society today. This has also been supported by the big technology companies that have turned this digitization, in many cases, into the only engine for business development today. You can no longer go to the bank to make your inquiries in a physical way since the digital revolution and that is causing big problems among people who are not used to, or do not want this digitization (the best example can be found in the campaign "I am old but not dumb" who wanted society to help older people who do not have the same facility with digitization).

That is why the connection that this fourth industrial revolution carries has become an element of possibility or of problems due to its excessive use. Combining these two aspects is the key for today's society and this leads to the challenge of being able to disconnect at certain times as we have seen during the pandemic.

This challenge, which is a problem, can become an opportunity to develop Digital Well-Being in inland or rural tourism in which Castilla y León is the leader. As we have analyzed previously, this community is

the champion of a very characteristic tourism that, if it understands how to take advantage of it, can become the guide that many other communities can follow, since this type of digital wellness tourism is and will be more and more demanded by the different sectors of the digital society. There are already experiences in the Community of Castilla y Le3n of examples of this digital wellness tourism that are becoming authentic references within the sector and that are anticipated as the model to be developed, but for this there must be good communication that enhances the existence of that type of tourism to bring it closer to those consumers who seek to understand the possibility of communing the digital with disconnection as an element of promoting their health and developing spaces for mental relaxation. The Castilian-Leonese spaces are ideal for this new tourism and are clearly anticipated as preferential places to continue having differential tourist experiences.

All this new role that Castilla y Le3n is already exercising and that it is going to spearhead would be of no use if there were no communication of what has been done. It is at this point where we can emphasize another of the characteristic elements of this community, since the local and regional media, so developed in recent years, play an important role in this process as authentic transmitters of the entire experience. The new digital wellness tourism must be able to reach the consumer, so communication is essential. That is why the communication model wisely developed in this community in recent years is key to promoting this new tourism model in this community.

What is local becomes a fundamental part of information and fulfills the necessary disseminating role that these new experiences need so that they can continue in this hyperconnected world. It is important that most of these types of spaces that have already developed this new type of digital wellness tourism are small spaces that feel supported by local and regional media. That is why the large tourism models that are presented in large media outlets have not yet managed to adapt this new tourism model, which is going to become one of the characteristics of the new leisure models.

Experiences such as those developed in Castilla y Le3n with its development model in this new field of tourism are going to be like a flame in the forest that spreads to all places and presents this community as a tourist reference for this new model of the tourism business which fulfills not only an economic role but also a social role.

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